

Ferric-Sulphoanthranilic Acid Complex

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The first and second dissociation constants of 5-sulphoanthranilic acid have been determined from *pH*-titration at $\mu = 0.1 M$. The thermodynamic second dissociation constants have also been determined by spectrophotometry and *pH*-titration at different ionic strengths with suitable extrapolation. The composition of Ferric-sulphoanthranilic acid complex was found to be 1 : 1 by Job's method of continuous variation. The stability constant of the complex and the second dissociation constant of the ligand have been determined at three different temperatures from which other thermodynamic parameters have been calculated.

Anthranilic acid, though may be regarded as a suitable bidentate ligand due to the favourable disposition of the—NH₂ and—COOH groups, its applicability as an analytical reagent is limited due to its poor solubility in water. The solubility of this reagent, however, is greatly enhanced by the introduction of the sulphonic acid group.

Suitability of 5-sulphoanthranilic acid as an analytical reagent was examined by Harris and Sweet¹. They determined the dissociation constant of the carboxylic group and the stability constants of different bivalent metal complexes from *pH*-titration studies assuming sulphonic acid group to be completely dissociated.

Zehner and Sweet² tried to use it as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric estimation of ferric ion in solution. They measured absorption due to the ferric complex of the ligand at *pH* = 4.0 at 455 *mμ* against the reagent and has a maximum value at *pH* = 4.0.

We report in this communication the second dissociation constant of the acid as measured by *pH*-titration and spectrophotometry. The spectra of acid in the low *pH*-regions indicate that sulphonic acid group is not completely dissociated. We, therefore, tried to determine both the first and second dissociation constants by *pH*-titration.

The composition of the Ferric-sulphoanthranilic acid complex has been determined and the dissociation constant of the ligand as well as its ferric complex have been determined at three different temperatures from which the thermodynamic properties for the dissociation and complexation reaction have been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Sulphoanthranilic acid was prepared by the modified method of Harris and Sweet. The purity of the sample was estimated by determining by a titration procedure the equivalent weight of the acid which agreed within 0.2% of the theoretical value.

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1. W. F. Harris and T. R. Sweet, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2893.

2. J. M. Zehner and T. R. Sweet, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 198.

A freshly prepared solution of sulphoanthranilic acid was always used. Ferric perchlorate was prepared by repeated evaporation of Ferric chloride with HClO_4 till the solution was free from chloride ion. The iron-content of the solution was estimated iodometrically as well as with dichromate solution. NaClO_4 was prepared from caustic soda and perchloric acid solutions. Chemicals used were of reagent grade. Solutions were made with double-distilled water.

For the determination of the second dissociation constant of the acid, a known volume of the stock sulphoanthranilic acid was mixed with calculated amount of standard caustic soda solution so that after neutralising the sulphonic acid group completely, the carboxyl group was also half-neutralised and the volume was made upto the mark. To measure $p\text{H}$ at half-neutralisation of the carboxyl group at different ionic strengths (from and below $\mu = 0.1 M$), a number of solutions were prepared in which the same amount of the above solution was mixed with requisite amount of potassium chloride solution.

5-sulphoanthranilic acid did not show any absorption in the visible region but absorbed strongly in the U.V. region. The absorption curves of the acid in the anionic form (A^{2-}) and molecular form (HA^-) were obtained by measuring the spectra in excess acid (HClO_4) and in excess alkali (NaOH) solution. Both the forms have two maxima. The band at $260 m\mu$ is present in both the forms. The second absorption band is at $316 m\mu$ for the ionic form and at $334 m\mu$ for the molecular form. The spectrum of the pure anionic form (A^-) was obtained without any difficulty but the absorbancy of the molecular form (HA^-) was found to change as the $p\text{H}$ was lowered. It is reasonable to assume that under the experimental $p\text{H}$ s (from $p\text{H}$ 2.5 and below)— SO_3H group is not completely dissociated. The variation of o.d. with increase in acid concentration suggests that in presence of excess acid a considerable amount of the acid is present as H_2A rather than HA^- , the concentration of which decreases as the $p\text{H}$ of the solution is diminished. From the $p\text{H}$ -titration study, the pK_{2T} was found to be 4.70 at 33° . Hence absorbancy of the solution at $p\text{H}$ close to 2 was taken to be that of the molecular form (HA^-) where the contribution to the absorbancy due to the presence of slight amount of H_2A may be neglected. The validity of our assumption that the presence of H_2A is negligible around $p\text{H}$ '2' is demonstrated by the fact that we have calculated separately the pK of HA^- taking o.d.s. at $p\text{H}$ s 1.85 and 2.32 as those for pure HA^- form respectively. The values from the two sets are very close which suggests that H_2A though present must be very small under the conditions of our experiment.

O.D. measurements were carried out at wavelengths 340 and 350 $m\mu$'s.

For the determination of pK_2 the o.d.s of 5-sulphoanthranilic acid ($\approx 2 \times 10^{-4} M$) in a number of buffers with $p\text{H}$'s ranging from 3.72 to 5.57³ and 2.32 and 1.85 ($\text{HCl} + \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$) and in slightly alkaline medium were measured. The blank solutions were of the same composition as in the experimental solutions except the ligand. The optical densities of the solutions were measured at three different temperatures viz., 20° , 30° and 40° at wavelengths 340 and 350 $m\mu$'s using matched quartz cells of 1 cm path length.

For the simultaneous determination of the first and second dissociation constants of the 5-sulphoanthranilic acid by $p\text{H}$ -titrations, definite amounts of the acid were taken in a series of volumetric flasks, neutralized to different extents

with caustic soda in different cases and diluted upto the mark, the ionic strength of the solutions was kept constant (0.1 *M*) with KCl solution. Dilution effect was avoided and *pH*'s were measured.

The composition of the complex was determined by the Job's method of continuous variation below *pH* 2 (to avoid hydrolysis of Fe³⁺ ions and also polynuclear complexes), at 420 and 450 *mμ*'s with different concentrations of ferric ion and the ligand. The results always indicate a 1 : 1 complex below *pH* 2. For each set of measurement *pH* was maintained constant.

The extinction coefficient of the complex was determined from the measurements of o.d.'s of solutions containing 100 to 200 fold excess of the ligand to different amounts of Fe³⁺ ion at these wavelengths against the reagent blank. Under the condition, the concentration of the complex could be taken to be equal to that of the ferric ion which was further confirmed by the fact that for the same concentration of ferric ion containing 120 to 200 times excess of the ligand, the o.d. readings were same. The constancy of the o.d. readings further indicate that under this condition only one complex is formed. The mean molar coefficient values are 1172 ± 2 and 1114 ± 2 at 420 and 450 *mμ*'s respectively.

For the determination of the stability constant of ferric sulphoanthranilic acid complex, o.d.'s of the solutions containing different amounts of ferric perchlorate and sulphoanthranilic acid were measured at wavelengths 420 *mμ* and 450 *mμ*. Calculated amount of NaClO₄ solution was added to maintain the ionic strength of the solution constant at 0.1 *M*. The *pH*'s of the solutions varied from 1.84–1.92. Measurements were taken at 22°, 32° and 41° respectively. *pH* measurements were taken with a Cambridge bench type battery operated *pH*-meter and o.d. readings with a Beckman D.U. spectrophotometer fitted with a thermostatic device.

RESULTS

The dissociation reactions for the 5-sulphoanthranilic acid may be written as

and

For the determination of the second dissociation constant, we have taken the *pH*s of half-neutralized acid so that

$$pK_{2T} = pH + \log \frac{f_{\text{HA}^-}}{f_{\text{A}^{=}}} \quad (3)$$

$\log \frac{f_{\text{A}^{=}}}{f_{\text{HA}^-}}$ can be calculated with the help of Davies⁴ equation. The thermodynamic dissociation constant was as well determined by extrapolating the *pK* values at different ionic strengths against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$ to zero ionic strength. The value of *pK*_{2*T*} is 4.70 at 33°.

The *pK*_{2*T*} have also been determined from spectrophotometric measurements⁵. The *pK*_{2*T*} values measured at three different temperatures 20°, 30° and 40° are given in the Table 1.

4. C. W. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.

5. S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *This Journal*, 1964, 41, 469.

K_{1T} and K_{2T} have been determined by *pH*-titration using the standard procedure used by various workers⁶. The average values of K_1 and K_2 are 2.77×10^{-2} ($pK_1 = 1.56$) and 5.29×10^{-5} ($pK_2 = 4.28$) at $\mu = 0.1 M$ at 25° . The thermodynamic values are :

$$pK_{1T} = 1.67 \quad \text{and} \quad pK_{2T} = 4.61 \quad \text{at} \quad 25^\circ.$$

Stability constant of the ferric complex : The equilibrium constant for the 1 : 1 complex of Fe(III) and sulpho-anthranilic acid,

is given as,

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{FeA}^+] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] \times [\text{HA}^-]} \times \frac{f_{\text{FeA}^+} \times f_{\text{H}^+}}{f_{\text{Fe}^{3+}} \times f_{\text{HA}^-}} = K_c K_f \quad (5)$$

During the experiment the ionic strength was maintained constant at $0.1 M$ (concentration of the complex being very small, its contribution towards the ionic strength is neglected), K_f is thus fixed. K_c 's can be calculated from the optical densities of various solutions, the extinction coefficients, K_1 and K_2 of the acid.

The measurements were taken at three different temperatures, namely 22° , 32° and 41° . Since K_1 is known only at one temperature, the temperature coefficient of the sulphonic acid group is taken to be the same as that for the second dissociation of H_2SO_4 from the work of Young, Klotz and Singletary⁷.

With this assumption, we determined the K_c values at different temperatures. The values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

System	Temp. °C	Equilibrium constant	
		at $\mu = 0.1 M$	Thermodynamic
$\text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{A}^{2-}$			
(i) <i>pH</i> -titration extrapolation method.	33°		2.0×10^{-5}
(ii) Spectrophotometric method.	20		$2.04(\pm 0.10) \times 10^{-5}$
	30		$2.24(\pm 0.10) \times 10^{-5}$
	40		$2.46(\pm 0.10) \times 10^{-5}$
$\text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{A}^-$	25°	2.77×10^{-2}	2.14×10^{-2}
$\text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{A}^{2-}$ (simultaneous determination from <i>pH</i> -titration)	25°	5.29×10^{-5}	2.46×10^{-5}
$\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}^+ + \text{H}^+$	22°	0.200 ± 0.006	1.79 ± 0.06
	32°	0.247 ± 0.008	2.21 ± 0.07
	41°	0.305 ± 0.010	2.74 ± 0.08
$\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{A}^{2-} \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}^+$	22°	4.49×10^3	8.56×10^4
	32°	5.05×10^3	9.65×10^4
	41°	5.68×10^3	10.92×10^4

6. S. Glasstone—An introduction to electrochemistry, Van Nostrand Company Inc. East West Ed. 1955, p. 326.

7. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, Electrolyte solutions, Butterworths Scientific Publication, Sec. Ed., 1959, p. 387.

The formation of Ferric-Sulphoanthranilic can be written as

and the corresponding concentration formation constant as

$$K = \frac{[\text{FeA}^+]}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] \times [\text{A}^-]} \quad (7)$$

This is also given in Table 1. The thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_a for the reaction (4) can be easily calculated from K_e since f_{FeA^+} can be assumed to be equal to f_{HA^-} as they are of the same charge type and f_{H^+} and $f_{\text{Fe}^{3+}}$ calculated by Davies equation.

The thermodynamic K_a and K_T calculated in the way described before are also given in Table 1. The evaluation of ΔH 's for the reactions (2), (4) and (6) have been made from the slope of the plot of $-\log K$ against $1/T$. From ΔH and ΔG values, ΔS values are calculated. These are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

System	$\mu = 0.1 M$	ΔG in K cal/mole	ΔH in K cal/mole	ΔS in e.u.
$\text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{A}^{2-}$	20°	6.28	1.68	-15.8
$\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{HA}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}^+ + \text{H}^+$	22°	0.940	4.14	10.8
$\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{A}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{FeA}^+$	22°	-4.925	2.29	24.4

DISCUSSIONS

The second dissociation constant of sulphoanthranilic acid reported by Harris and Sweet¹ is 2.00×10^{-5} at 35° ($pK = 4.70$) assuming the sulphonic group to be completely dissociated. It is not clear whether the value is thermodynamic or not.

The thermodynamic pK_T value for the second dissociation constant from pH measurements in the present work is 4.70 at 33°. The pK_T values obtained from spectrophotometric measurements using Davies equation are 4.69 at 20°, 4.65 at 30° and 4.61 at 40° respectively. The values for pK_{1T} and pK_{2T} of the ligand obtained by us from pH -titration are 1.67 and 4.61 (using Davies equation) at 25°. It is known that the sulphonic acid group in aromatic compounds is a little stronger than HSO_4^- which is actually observed in practice. The dissociation constant for HSO_4^- is 1.04×10^{-2} at 25° whereas the value for the dissociation constant of sulphonic acid group is 2.14×10^{-2} at 25°.

Considering the different techniques used in the determination of the dissociation constant, the values may be regarded to be quite satisfactory.

The equilibrium constant for reaction (4) is 0.2004 at $\mu = 0.1 M$ at 22° (thermodynamic value is 1.789 at 22°) and for the formation constant (6) the value is 4.49×10^3 at $\mu = 0.1 M$ whereas K , thermodynamic is 8.56×10^4 at 22°.

A comparison of the values is not possible as no such data are available in the literature.

The values suggest that the complex is very weak. This also gives us an idea regarding the strengths of the bonds that the Fe^{3+} nitrogen bonds ($\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+} - \text{O}$) are weaker than the Fe^{3+} oxygen ($\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+} - \text{O}$) bonds.

Coming to the other thermodynamic quantities, it has been found that the second dissociation of the acid as well as for the reaction (4) and (6) is endothermic meaning ΔH values are unfavourable in both the cases. The value of entropy is -15.7 e.u. for the reaction (1) in good agreement with the values generally obtained for carboxyl groups.

The entropy values for the dissociation of acid is unfavourable whereas for the complex formation reactions are favourable. These facts can be explained in terms of Frank and Evans⁸ concept of iceberg.

In the dissociation reaction, H^+ ion and doubly charged $\text{A}^{=}$ ions are formed which have an ordering influence on the solvent molecules, restricting the degrees of freedom leading to the decrease in entropy.

For the reaction (4) and (6), the charge on the trivalent Fe^{3+} ion has a greater ordering effect on the solvent, the net result is the increase of entropy in both the reactions as there is neutralisation of charges but this effect would be more pronounced in case of (6) where neutralisation involves a triply charged Ferric ion and doubly charged Sulphoanthranilium ion.

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8. H. S. Frank and M. Evans, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.